

The Zamindari Durga Pujas from the 18th – 19th Centuries of Calcutta

Diptangshu Dutta Gupta

MA in History, Jadavpur University. Currently enrolled in School of Buddhist Studies, Nalanda
University

Abstract: This paper interprets the zamindari Durga Pujas of 18th and 19th Centuries Calcutta as historical texts that reflect Bengal’s intertwined trajectories of religion, politics, and modernity. It traces the transformation of worship of Goddess Durga—from tribal and martial cults of the goddess to Brahmanical incorporation, royal patronage, and finally, the grand domestic pujas of Calcutta’s elite households or Zamindars. Focusing on families such as the Sabarna Raychoudhuris of Barisha, the Debs of Shobhabazar, the Daws of Jorasanko, and the Ghoses of Pathuriaghata, the study explores how these ritual spectacles functioned as instruments of social legitimacy, colonial negotiation, and expressions of evolving urban identity of colonial Calcutta. Drawing upon textual, architectural, and visual evidence, it situates the pujas within broader shifts in Bengal’s sociopolitical fabric—from post-Plassey collaboration and the rise of the “babu culture” to the emergence of nationalist symbolism and barowari or community pujas. The paper further examines how colonial modernity, Western artistic realism, and indigenous creativity reshaped the goddess’s iconography and ritual space, culminating in Durga’s transformation into a metaphor of the nation. By reading festivals and traditions as living archives, the paper demonstrates how Kolkata’s Durga Puja continues to embody an important part of Bengal’s historical consciousness—an enduring synthesis now globally recognized as UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage.

Keywords: Durga, Zamindar, Bonedi, Calcutta, Colonial, Puja

Devyā yayā tatam idaṁ jagad ātmaśaktyā
niḥśeṣadevagaṇaśaktisamūhamūrtyā
tām Ambikām akhiladevamaharṣipūjyām
bhaktyā (pra) natāḥ sma vidadhātu śubhāni sā naḥ

The goddess, who stretched out this world by her power,
Whose body comprises the entire powers of all the hosts of gods,
Her, Ambika, worthy of worship by all gods and great ṛṣis,
We bow before in faith; may she ordain blessings for us!

- Devi Mahatmyam (4.3) in Markandeya Purana 81.3

Introduction: From Forests to Forts to Royal Estates – the Many Patrons of the Goddess

On 15th December 2021, the UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage issued a press release inscribing Durga Puja of Kolkata on the list of intangible heritage –

“Today, the Intergovernmental Committee for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage inscribed ‘Durga Puja in Kolkata’ on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity during its 16th session, taking place virtually from 13 to 18 December this year.”¹

Today’s Durga Puja is not a celebration that transcends religious and social backgrounds. Its inception as a UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage in 2021 is because of the long history of Durga Puja the city of Calcutta has gone through. The city wakes up at night during the days of festivities not as the ‘largest public art festival’ but also where the opulence of the goddess or Devi comes to life through art, creativity and devotion. Before the emergence of popular theme-based Durga Pujas in Calcutta from the early 2000s or the 21st Century onwards, it was the bonedi or zamindari houses that dominated the festive landscape in Bengal in the autumn season. It is noteworthy that Durga Puja was first commemorated as a ‘festival’ in the 18th century on the grounds of British victory at Plassey in 1757 at the Shobhabazar Rajbari in Calcutta. Prior to the beginning of Durga Puja in Shobhabazar Rajbari, it was not a festival, but an annual ritual of Hindu worship of the mother goddess Durga. The epithet of festival or ‘utshob’ got associated following the Company victory at Plassey and Nabakrishna Deb’s foundation of Durga Puja at his estate. Since then onwards Durga Puja became ‘Durgotsav’. Her celebration in modern Bengal was to commemorate the martial victory. Durga was indeed a deity venerated by Indian kings and rulers in times of wars and sieges. Her military exploits and achievements against the demons comes forth to light in the popular text of Devi Mahatmyam which forms a part of the 6th Century text Markandeya Purana. Durga, is a central deity to śaktism and has been an integral part to Bengali cultural identity. Devi along with Brahma and Śiva forms an important triad in Hindu Puranic tradition. However, the origins of Durga are non-Brahmanical and it is only around 6th century CE that Brahmanism began a conscious and highly creative process of integrating this non-Vedic goddess into the Brahmanical pantheon. This was evident in Bengal which was out of Vedic-Aryan influence until the late Gupta period where Brahmanism was forced to reckon goddess traditions in its fold so as to strike roots in the region. Though the name ‘Durga’ appears in the Taittirīya Āraṇyaka of the Black Yajurveda 10.1 and the Ṛg Veda Khilas 10.127, these contain a Durgāśūkta, in which she is invoked as goddess Durgā but only through a specific set of adjectives like agnivarṇām, jvalantim, vairocanīm. According to Sāyaṇa, the commentator to the Black Yajurveda these are mantras that are to be recited to remove undesirables or obstacles (aniṣṭas). Since the word ‘Durga’ also means adversity, throughout Durga’s early development she and her rituals were essentially connected to averting or managing periods of communal crises. Sarkar (2017, p. 15) argues that warrior-goddess worship was intrinsically a religion whose domain was danger. In this case, this makes her invocation quite justifiable with epithets like Durgottarini and Durgatinasini. The Taittirīya Āraṇyaka (X.1.7.8) mentions how the goddess is invoked as a virgin girl or kumārī, where the earliest textual roots of Kumari Puja lie. There she is referred to as Kanyākumārī as the geographical southernmost tip of India (Cape Comorin). Kunal Chakrabarti notes how the role of the goddess was marginal in the Vedic Literature (Chakrabarti, 2001, p. 166).² The result was the Devi-Mahatmyam which forms a part of Markandeya Purana composed around c. 6th Century CE. The Devi-Mahatmyam details the martial character and military exploits of the goddess. Durga’s worship was already prevalent in Bengal as part of śakta traditions. Her historical origins from literary sources state that she was a deity who was revered by the hill tribes of Vindhya mountains in Central India before she was appropriated as a prominent deity equal to that of Viṣṇu and Śiva under the Gupta Age (Sarkar 2017). Yokochi’s (2004) work showed that the legend of the goddess Kauśiki Vindhyaśinī contained in the oldest version of that work represented the stage of Durgā’s history, around the 7th century, when she had been elevated from a formerly minor martial goddess of the Vindhya mountains into a supreme ruler of the gods. By placing on an early recension of the Skandapurāṇa, Yokochi showed the origins of the warrior goddess cult lay in ‘the social segment centred

on kings and the warrior class'. Durga was patronised by tribes before Brahmanical appropriation placed her in the circuit of imperial kings and rulers who invoked her in wars and sieges. Bihani Sarkar (2017, p. 14) shows how the notion of 'Heroic Saktism' was reinforced through the *Devi Mahatmyam*, which formed the archetypal text of imperial kingship –

“It conveyed the idea of the war-goddess as imperial metaphor: she is an image of the king himself in his most potent form, the *cakravartīn* —‘the one at the centre of the circle’—unifying vassal states as she unifies smaller goddesses, granted power and light by the gods and appointed by them to restore Dharma, the pristine true order. Even though empire was no longer the dominant political framework in the context of the ‘new world’, heroic Śāktism perpetuated its myth for the cultivation of transcendent kingship by smaller kingdoms with aspirations to connect themselves to a broader network of classical civilization.”

But by the time her worship began in the zamindari palaces or *rajbaris* of Modern Bengal, we come to notice the transition of her patronage to worship. What started as a worship of a tribal deity later became a deity venerated by kings and warriors before in the modern period she came to be worshipped in the elite households of the Bengali zamindaris. Bengal has been the heartland of the ever-evolving śākta worship in historical and late-historical era. The earliest Durga Puja in Bengal was arranged by Raja Kangsanarayan of Tahirpur, who was advised by one of the wise brahmins to make arrangements for Durga Puja as a conduct of sanctification abiding by the puranas (Guha-Thakurta 2015). Calcutta and its surroundings also suggested the prevalence of goddess traditions in early or pre-British Calcutta. Three temples noteworthy for being pilgrim spots in this region were – “Betaia Chandi” temple at Betor, “Sarvamangala Devi” temple at Chitpur, and “Kali temple” at Kalighat. (Sen 2019, p. 82). This Betaia Chandi temple was both a halt station for traders and trade-center itself – where merchants came to pay homage to the goddess and where they stopped as a temporary halt for their shopping and rest before they would set out on their onward journey.³ Ranjit Sen mentions that a goddess-ridden culture was gradually developing from the 16th Century under the sea-faring merchants who propitiated goddess by worship and it is where by the banks of Ganges the temple of Dakshineswar eventually grew up as a base for mother-worship in the second half of the nineteenth century with Ramakrishna Paramahansa at its centre (Sen 2019, p. 82 – 83). Though Durga Puja became a festival from 1757 onwards, its consciousness has continually been shaped and re-shaped and accommodated itself in the changing social and political conditions (Deb 2021, p. 91).

Again, in the course of late 19th and early 20th centuries onwards as anti-colonial nationalism will center around the Durga Puja festivities, it will enable the pujas to acquire a secular status in society where a selective array of its discourses and rites were used to define a political community. Hindu discourse and practices were used to strengthen a language of anti-colonial nationalism in Bengal from the late nineteenth century (Bhattacharya 2007, pp. 919 – 962). The course of the 20th century will witness how the image of Durga gradually transformed into a nationalist image representing the nation-state. This nationalist projection of Durga enables one to understand the secular aspect of the festivities where political agendas of the Hindu-revivalist era are expressed. If the zamindars and the *babus* organised Durga pujas at their estates in the 18th Century to legitimise their social authority and forge alliances with the British at their residencies, then these will be the same *babus* who will organise festivities at their estates where they will celebrate Durga Puja to propagate (Hindu) nationalism and vis-à-vis acquire social legitimisation of their support to anti-colonial nationalism. With the city in transformation in colonial and post-colonial times, the process of festivalisation of Durga Puja also helped to transform the city landscape as Negrier (2014) describes the processes of festivalisation wherein a cultural activity that was earlier held regularly at particular times or seasons is reconfigured as a new event. Gibson and Stewart (2009) state that it is an annual event to celebrate some aspect of local culture that becomes an unusual point of convergence of people. Cudny (2014, p. 43) points out that festivals create in the urban landscape space for temporary cultural consumption and transforms an ordinary everyday space into a cultural space occupied for the festival. It would be in this context where

Durga Puja emerges as a festival that becomes central to Kolkata's urban identity transforming its urbanscape during the timeframe of the Durga Puja and the branding of the city of Kolkata as a site of modern creative cultures (De 2021, pp. 114 – 115). This research is an outcome of surveys I did in selected zamindari houses of Calcutta during the days of Durga Puja in the years of 2023-2024 supported with secondary sources.

Calcutta as a site of Sakti Worship before Colonial era Durga Pujas

Figure 1. View of Chitpore Road in North Calcutta by Thomas and William Daniell in 1797, hand-tinted engraving on paper. The English artists Thomas Daniell and his nephew William Daniell, toured India in the 1700s to document various parts of the country. These 'views' were later reproduced in their book of paintings called *Oriental Scenery: One Hundred and Fifty Views of the Architecture, Antiquities, and Landscape Scenery of Hindoostan*. The house of a Bengali merchant at Chitpore, an indigenous marketplace in north Calcutta, intrigued Thomas Daniell because of its mixed style of architecture. According to Daniell, it combined Islamic ornamentation with a turret that was 'an unsuccessful attempt at the Grecian'. While people go about their business on the streets, grey clouds rise in the blue skies almost in anticipation of a heavy downpour. (Source: Picture by author, this image is now kept in the custody of DAG Museums)

Calcutta was not found by the British. Rather before them Armenian traders and the Seths and Basak merchants and the indigenous people contributed to the formation of the city. Therefore Calcutta's rise was facilitated by economic forces of those times. It was only after the British possession of the three villages of Kalikata, Sutanuti, and Govindapur when Calcutta took the shape of a rough and ready settlement that would serve the dual purpose of a trade centre and a habitation of the English traders and sailors. This transformed Calcutta into a fort-centric garrisoned town (Sen 2019, pp. 89 – 90). The Navaratna or Nine Jewels Temple built by Govindaram Mitra, the "Black Zamindar" of Calcutta was another temple which in the middle of the eighteenth century that was quite popular in its times. Later it came to be overshadowed by the temples of Dakshina Kali and Sarvamangala or Chittesvari, respectively situated at Kalighat (see figure 2) and Chitpur (see figure 1) (Sen 2019, p. 171; Chaudhuri

1973, p. 16). A biographer of Calcutta, “called it by the name of Kalikshetra. It extended from Bahula (now Behala) to Dakshinasar. According to the puranas a portion of the mangled corpse of Sati or Kali fell somewhere within that boundary whence the place was called Kalikshetra. Calcutta is a corruption (apabrahmsa) of Kalikhsetra” (Newman 1875, p. 1; Nair 1986, p. 28). According to Sen (2021, p. 175) this association with the puranic mythology was enough in itself to give Calcutta a boost towards its growth as a religious centre or as a pilgrim town. Thus Calcutta has always been a site for śaktī worship and people’s consciousness and devotion towards devī or śaktī gave full expression to the emergence of Durga Pujas in the 18th Century.

Figure 2. Left – Kalighat, chromolithograph on paper, 1930. An advertising poster for The Eastern Bengal Railway Company, one of the many which owned and operated railway tracks in colonial India. The print features Kalighat temple, dedicated to the Hindu Goddess Kali, in Calcutta, with its name inscribed in Devanagari at the lower edge. The presence of a crowd of devotees within the temple complex was aimed at emphasising the religious site’s popularity, and an attempt to lure Hindu crowds from the northern part of the subcontinent to Calcutta, in order to boost ticket sales for the company. Right – Colour Etching of Goddess Kali of Kalighat Temple by Haren Das in 1970. (Source: Picture clicked by author, this image is now kept in the custody of DAG Museums)

The 18th Century witnessed Durga pujas which were no longer simple marks of ritual purity but rather huge ostentations pageants bestowing social authority on the new banias. The puja fused performance, fantasy, and aspirations in a seemingly unending theatre of dramatic spectacle. Popular songs, music, and dancing forced the wider community irrespective of religion to acknowledge the presence of the goddess. These bands of singers were the famous baijis, nautch girls and the new urban poets of contemporary society. The entertainers themselves were crucial in denoting a secular urban status to religion (Bhaumik 2019, p. 18). In these zamindari pujas colloquially known as ‘bonedi pujas’, the thakurdalaan or worship pavilions (for example see figure 3) were the centres where babu-company alliances were forged. The thakurdalaan is the central space of the houses of these landed magnates which was the centre of both religious and political activities. Every zamindari house has a main entrance which directly leads to the thakurdalaan surrounded by colonnades on both opposite sides while the other side which directly faces the entrance is an elevated platform marked by intricately

arched colonnades where the deity worship was conducted. It is here where the public image of Durga was first constructed in urban space with the coming of the British in the 18th Century. The banias or natives who closely worked with the British continued to arrange these grand pujas right from the 18th to all throughout the 19th centuries. ‘Thakur Dalaan’ came to accommodate the sacred rituals which also became a space for public gathering. Zamindars possessed the financial credibility to organise this socio-religious function and sustain it over the years and the Asiatic Journal of 1816 describes wealthier Bengalees opening up their reception for every class of the inhabitants of Calcutta (Mitra and Roy 2021, p. 23 – 24). It is worth noticing that the emergence of Durga Puja as a festival also happens where every zamindari family in Calcutta has their own set of traditions and set of rituals they follow under the umbrella of prescriptive texts of Hindu Scriptural Literature. This what makes the Durga Puja of one zamindari family different from the other one. Such articulation of new ideas and traditions with the advent of colonialism also contributed to the urbanisation of Calcutta in a festive landscape.

Figure 3. The Thakurdalaans at Shobhabazar Rajbari. Above is the puja which Nabakrishna Deb himself started in 1757 after the Plassey Battle. Below is the puja which was started by Nabakrishna’s biological son in 1790 by Rajkrishna Deb.

Makers of Pre-British Calcutta – The Raychoudhuris of Barisha in Bohulapuri or Behala

In the early days of development in Calcutta, the Sabarna Raychoudhuris of Barisha (now in the Behala area of Kolkata) were the first to perform Durga Puja. According to their family history, the founder of this family was a revenue officer under King Pratapaditya of Jessore, who switched his support to the Mughals under Aurangzeb and acquired a large part of the territory of Calcutta (Deb 2021, p. 91). This is because Pratapaditya murdered Basanta Ray, who was the uncle of Lakhikanta Majumdar.⁴ Later when Lakhikanta and the Mughal subedar Mansingh allied to defeat Pratapaditya, Mansingh awarded Lakhikanta the title of 'Ray' (meaning auspiciousness) and 'Chaudhuri' (meaning land grants) from where the family came to be known as Raychaudhuris (Chaudhuri 2022, pp. 42 – 43). This puja was started by Lakhikanta Majumdar and unlike other bonedi pujas, this puja was open to the common public. Family history also states that during the rule of the Sena Dynasty in South Bengal, Shishupati Gangopadhyay who was then the head of the family received the title of 'Best of Kulins' and the area of Kālīshetra as a royal grant from King Ballal Sena.⁵ That time Kālīshetra roughly coincided with today's from Ariahdaha to South Calcutta's Behala (which was the known as Bohulāpurī). By the 13th Century oral sources state that this entire area of 16 miles came under the jurisdiction of the Sabarna Raychoudhuris (Chaudhuri 2022, p. 39). It must also be remembered that they were the patrons of the Kalighat Kali Temple in Kalighat. It was from this area that Charles Iyer, the son-in-law of Job Charnock on 10 November 1698 acquired the villages of Kalikata, Gobindapur and Sutanuti against an annual lease of Rs. 1300 from the Sabarna Raychaudhuris (Chaudhuri 2022, p. 36) in the Kachrabari of the Raychaudhuris, popularly known as the Aatchala of the Chaudhuris whose only remnants of 8 red pillars remain today (see figures 5 and 6) (Chaudhuri 2022, pp. 46 – 47). Among the eight houses of the Raychaudhuris where Durga Puja is done (for example see figures 4 and 7), this is where the most popular one happens. During the time when the family flourished at its peak the most spectacular event was the ritual of bali or sacrifice – where goat sacrifice happened on every days of the puja ending with a buffalo sacrifice on the day of Dashami. The family's opulence was not only witnessed how they performed Durga Puja or how they patronised the Kali Temple in Kalighat but also from their infrastructural contributions like the road which they built from Halisahar to Barisha via Kalighat.

Figure 4. The Mejobari Puja of the Raychaudhuris.

Figure 5. The puja of Kachrabari of the Raychaudhurs, popularly known as the Aatchala of the Chaudhurs. This is where Lakhikanta Raychaudhuri leased out portions of Calcutta to Charles Iyer on an annual lease of 1300 Rupees.

Figure 6. The Kachrabari whose only 8 pillars remain today.

Figure 7. The Borobari (Elder House) Puja of the Raychaudhuris. Left – The thakudalaan of Borobari. Right – the Durga image of Borobari.

The Debs of Shobhabazar – Kingmakers of Early Colonial Bengal

The Deb family of Shobhabazar organised their first puja in 1757 after Nawab Siraj-ud-Daulah's fall at Plassey when Nabakrishna Deb, the bania of Robert Clive constructed his thakurdalaan at Deb Estate in Shobhabazar at Calcutta. Nabakrishna Deb's ancestors are said to have belonged from Kannauj and later settled in Karnasuvarna (near modern day Murshidabad) at the court of King Karnasenvijay Sriharidev where the Moudgalya gotra (one of the 7 gotras of the Deb family) came to reside in Jessore (now in Bangladesh) by the 15th century during the reign of Sultan of Bengal Hussain Shah. From there, the family under Ramcharan Deb by 1730-35 came to settle in Gobindapur village⁶ where they resided by the banks of the Ganges. Ramcharan dies in an encounter with local bandits after which the family led by Ramcharan's widowed wife decides to shift to Sutanuti by the Ganges where Nabakrishna later purchases a plot of land from Shobharam Basak. This is the plot of land where the current house and the thakurdalaan stands (see figure 3).⁷ The journals in those days like *The Bengal Hurkaru* on 12 October 1829, gave extensive coverage to amusements with special reference to the attendance of the British guests at Shobhabazar (Banerjee 2004, p. 36). From Robert Clive to Warren Hastings to Cornwallis and William Bentick, most of the Governor-Generals of Bengal and India have frequented this puja. But given the cosmopolitan and political nature of these pujas, where banias and zamindars asserted social authority in native society by organising such grand festivities, religious austerities were strictly adhered to in times of festivities. This was assured by the worship of Durga that was strictly followed as prescribed by the scriptures. Therefore even if the bonedi houses were centers of formation of alliances with the colonial officers and the native elites, Nabakrishna (see figure 8, left) ensured that like a revered goddess and a daughter of the house she shouldn't come into direct contact with the outsiders. Hence, he built the nachghar from where the thakurdalaan was clearly visible to the invited Britishers. There was a clear delineation between the outsiders (here the British) and the sacred world (of the goddess), although his puja was meant to commemorate the Plassey victory of the British. But as a bania, his actual intention was to assert his own socio-political authority in his society (see figure 8, right).

Figure 8. Left – Portrait of Nabakrishna Deb inside the thakudalaan. Right – the marble plaque at the entrance of Rajchandra’s House Puja which started in 1790. The marble plaque itself states the identity of Nabakrishna as the dewan of Clive.

Figure 9. The idol was decorated and dressed up in Daaker Saaj. It was the day of Tritya or the third day of Navaratri when I visited the house. (Source: Photo clicked by the author in 2024)

Figure 10. Interior of the thakurdalaan.

Figure 11. Swami Vivekananda addressing his first public gathering after his return from Chicago where he delivered his legendary speech at the World Parliament of Religions. He gave his first public address after his return to India at the Shobhabazar Rajbari in Calcutta under the patronage of Raja Binoykrishna Deb.

Religion from the very beginning was a part of the private sphere and was constantly concealed from interventions from the outsiders when it came under the direct purview of politics. From late 19th century in the revivalist discourse, as we see, nationalism ventured outside to challenge the colonial state after emerging inside the inner domain of the Hindu bourgeois public sphere, which was the domain of culture and religion. During the Durga Puja festivities from Shashti to Dashami, shehnai players play the shehnai at the nahbatkhana. Since rituals of the goddess (see figure 9) are done in the house as per Smarta tradition, no cooked food is offered to the deity. Rather dry fruits, lentils and 72 types of homemade sweets are offered. These homemade sweets are made in the Bhiyen Ghor, or the kitchen which is in the south direction of the house. Chefs come from Midnapore to cook. The influence of British symbolisms was also seen in this puja. For example, the image of the house which started in 1757 had a horse-faced lion (ghotok-mukhi shingho) (for example see figure 12) reminding that the Deb Family are Vaisnavites because their kuladevata is the Visnu Saligrama what they call as ‘Gopinath Jiu’. This puja was later taken over by Nabakrishna’s adopted son Gopimohan. While the puja of the house which started in 1790 when Nabakrishna’s own blood-related son Rajkrishna Deb was born, that lion image of the deity is of British style. Such lions often features in coat of arms. That lion image was covered in silver sheets which was once imported from Germany, now it is only painted in silver acrylic. One of the interesting facts of this house is that they don’t perform sindoor khela as they believe sindoor or dust vermilion is not something that should be played with. Rather they offer sindoor to the deity as part of ‘sindoor daan’ (offering the sindoor) as a holy ritual before bidding farewell to the goddess in the Ganges carrying her on shoulders on two bamboo poles.

Figure 12. An example of Ghotok-mukhi Shingho or horse-faced lion mostly worshipped by Vaisnavites. Note its body structure where a lean and flexible body of the horse has been hybridised with claws and sharp teeth of a lion. This image is from the smaller house right adjacent to the Pathuriaghata Rajbari.

Ramdulal Sarkar – The Americanised Zamindar

At a time when most of the zamindars were banias to the British, there were rare instances where within the precincts of Calcutta, zamindars served as banias to western but non-British traders in an English-dominated commercial scenario. One such case is Ramdulal Sarkar’s allegiance towards the Americans. He acquired his wealth by working under Madanmohan Dutta of Haatkholā Dutta House. Ramdulal Sarkar (see figure 15) later changes his title to Ramdulal De. He traded muslin textiles, indigo, pepper, jute, spices, sugar, tea – all of which were crucial commodities for the European markets. He started his puja in 1770 (see figure 13) and later passed down its responsibility to two of his sons, Pramathanath and Ashutosh (see figure 16 left and right), which results in the zamindari puja being nicknamed Chatubabu and Latubabu’s Puja. What is striking here is that Shaivite, Vaishnavite and Shakta customs all fuse here altogether at this puja. Like Shobhabazar Rajbari, there was also an earlier custom here

to fly a kingfisher bird, but now its clay images are immersed along with the deity on the last day of Durga Puja. This ritual was meant to let Shiva, the consort of Parvati or Durga know that the daughter of the house has departed for her in-laws house which is Kailasa, the abode of Shiva. She arrives as a mother but departs as a daughter when the festivities concludes. One must take note of how new customs and traditions centering the puja developed under different circumstances. These newly fabricated rituals were neither prescribed in the conventional scriptures nor were they practiced before. Durga Puja played a definite role in shaping and giving Calcutta her cosmopolitan character. This was an important change in the timing of the Durga Pujas in Bengal. This has been interpreted by scholars as a part of the ‘Sanskritization’ of the ritual event and its induction within the new structures of Brahmanical orthodoxy amidst the rising socio-political authority of Hindu land-owning magnates during the 17th and 18th centuries (Guha-Thakurta 2015, p. 3). Even P.J. Marshall of the New Cambridge School of History states that by the 18th Century the big zamindars came to constitute a distinct feature of Bengal’s socio-economic history (Marshall 1987, p. 58). Likewise, this period was crucial in the formulation of idol of goddess Durga in Kumartuli (the potter’s square/colony) as each bonedi family interpreted the ancient scriptures in distinct (and in their own) ways to give form to the idol of the goddess of their own houses, thus formulating specific formal attributes of goddess Durga along with her family tableau, while negotiating with the basic prescriptions of giving form to the Devi murti (Deb 2021, p. 92). Ultimately it gave rise to the portrayal of Durga as a mother and daughter that characterised an integral aspect of the nationalist discourse (for example see figure 35). The daughter will be married off as a newlywed wife upon whom the responsibility of her new family rests. This new woman is nabyanari who is entrusted to maintain the home and the family which extends as the nation-state which was still an embryo. The new woman was herself a bourgeois lady but unlike her husband, lacked rights and true freedom. She lacked an independent agency to voice her opinions. She was expected to dedicate herself fully towards conserving the spiritual and cultural prowess of the nation-state (which forms the inner domain of Partha Chatterjee’s argument) through which the nation can declare her ascendancy over the colonial state.⁸ This colonial state has colonised the natives through its technological, economic and political capabilities. This nationalist discourse that takes momentum from the mid-19th century onwards was left with the spiritual domain which wasn’t yet defiled by the colonial state (Chatterjee 1993, pp. 5 – 8). This is because of the colonial state’s support to introduce social reforms that was overturned by the Act of 1840.

Figure 13. The Durga image kept in an altar like designed throne what is termed as Singhasan. This is at Ramdulal Sarkar residence.

Figure 14. The thakurdalaan at Ramdulal Sarkar's Estate.

Figure 15. Portrait of Ramdulal Sarkar.

Figure 16. Left – Pramatha Nath Deb alias Latubabu; Right – Ashutosh Deb alias Chatubabu

Finally, this resulted in the rise of barowari or community pujas. Earlier the first recorded barowari pujo was started by the ‘twelve brahmin friends’ (baro yaar) in Guptipara in Hooghly District (now in West Bengal, India) when they were not allowed to participate in the puja of the elite zamindars. The Friend of India in May 1820 reported that “...[a] new species has been introduced within the last thirty years, called Barwaree .. about thirty years ago, at Goopti-para, near Santipoora.... a number of Brahmins formed an association for the celebration of a Pooja independently They elected twelve (baro) men as a committee from which circumstance it takes its name, and solicited subscription in all the surrounding villages” (Mitra and Roy 2021, p. 25). Such a development of a religious phenomenon in an evolving society allowed the common public with an opportunity to offer their devotion to the Devi (Deb 2022, p. 92). Gradually with the rise in barowari pujas, Durga Puja became a much more popular festival. Abhijeet Dutta has stated two vital points for the rise of Barowari pujas. In the first place, he argues, that due to the legislation introduced by the Company’s government in 1840, the Company’s officials were no longer able to participate in the religious festivals of the natives. Secondly, from the end of the first half of the 19th Century, European patronage of the Hindu Bengali Babus began to register a moderate decline. Another principal cause fomenting the start of the community or Barowari Pujas in Calcutta and its environs was the fall in the number of Durga Pujas in rich landlord families owing to constant litigation over property matters, among their numerous members or constituents (Dutta 2003, pp. 45 – 46). This caused huge economic losses among members of such families, resulting in fragmentation of many such households and permanently stopping the holding of Durga Puja in their residences.

Janbazaar – Where the Rani or Queen is Zamindar

In a predominant patriarchal society of those times, the house of the 19th Century philanthropist Rani Rashmoni (see figure 20) at Janbazaar (now in the area of Esplanade in Kolkata) stands out where a woman was the main patron behind a bonedi pujo. What is also fascinating is her social origins. She was a Kaivartta by caste. Kaivarttas were regarded as fisherman by caste and were marginalised by the upper castes in society. Earliest reference to Kaivarttas as fisherman are found from the Aśokan Inscriptions as kevatabhoga as early as third century BCE in the 5th Pillar Edict of Aśoka, where

emperor Aśoka issued an order to prevent the killing of fishes in the preserves of fishermen (kevatabhoga) (Basak, 1959, pp. 98 – 105). Though this puja was started in 1790 by Rashmoni's father-in-law and later was conducted by her husband Babu Rajchandra Das (after whom the Babughat is named in Calcutta's Strand Road by the Hooghly River) before she took up the baton. As I was conversing with the members of the current generation of the family, they described the image who is decked in 'sholapith-er daak-er shaaj'. The image of Durga is painted here in red colour resembling her ferocious and warrior like Candikā form described in the puranic texts (see figure 18). Unlike other houses who have their own moulds for making the face of Durga from clay, this house intricately shapes the face of Durga from hands every year without the use of any mould. The chalachitra or backdrop has Bengal pattachitra paintings depicting stories from the Mahabharata and the Bhagavata Purana (which mostly deals Krsna's childhood). Interestingly if one notices properly, the figures depicted in this chalachitra fighting the Mahabharata War are dressed in tight skirts and turbans – a reminiscent of the once Bengali nawabi and late-Mughal styles of dressing that was prevalent in 17th Century Bengal (see figure 19). One is led to the courtyard of the house from the door which is now surrounded by many shops on the street. Construction of this house started in 1805 which ended in 1820 under Pritiram Das (see figure 17), the father-in-law of Rashmoni. Many say that the name Janbazaar (of Esplanade area) has been derived from the apabrahmsa of the name of 'John' – an Englishman who used to reside in this area. In the year 1864, Ramakrishna Paramhansa himself was the priest here in Durga Puja rituals. A tradition which still survives today here is that Kumari Puja is conducted on all the three days of Saptami, Astami and Navami (Chakraborty 2022, p. 93). Rashmoni had a profound influence here and not just as the builder of the Dakshineswar Kali Temple.

Figure 17. The Thakurdalaan at Rashmoni's Janbazaar Rajbari

Figure 18. The idol at Rashmoni's House. Its height is quite gigantic like idols of Sarbojanin Pujas unlike idols of Bonedi Houses which are at a height till the length of a shoulder.

Figure 19. The chalachitra art at the backdrop of the images. Left – Scenes from Mahabharata where Draupadi was disrobed by Dushasana and the Kauravas are shown in action. Right – Scenes from Mahabharata and Bhagavata Purana where the Pandavas are shown to have killed the Kauravas and the gopis or milkmaids begging to Krsna to return their clothes respectively. Pattachitra art in this case highlighted both Mughal and Nawabi styles of dressing as prevalent in Early Modern Bengal showing a transition from Nawabi courtly culture to babu elitism.

Figure 20. Image of Rani Rashmoni.

Figure 21. Homemade sweets and Bengali snacks are offered as prasad to the goddess at Janbazaar.

Figure 22. Left – Entrance to the house of Rashmoni’s second daughter Kumari Chowdhury within the premises of Janbazaar Estate. Right – The Durga Puja at Kumari Chowdhury’s residence which was started in 1884.

Jorasanko Shibkrishna Daw House – Where Goddess comes for Sṛngāra

With the growing popularity of Durga Puja in Colonial Calcutta – urban myths also came to be articulated among the Bengali population. Devi in Bengal is revered both as a daughter and a mother who annually visits her parent’s house from Siva’s abode, i.e., Kailasa. When she comes to Calcutta she first visits the house of Jorasanko Shibkrishna Daw House to get dressed in fine clothes and decked in stunning jewellery. Then she visits Abhaycharan Mitra’s House in Kumartuli to have an amazing feast of a long list of delicacies specially prepared for her. Unfortunately, no lineage survives today of Abhaycharan Mitra and the house lies in ruins in Kumartuli right beside the studios where all Durga idols are made (see figure 25 right). After having a wonderful feast, she finally visits Shobhabazar Rajbari to witness dance and musical performances in the evening of the nauch girls who were brought from Benaras. The myth shows that among all the bonedi Durga Pujas of Calcutta, these three houses stood out amongst the others. One reason of course is the way they celebrated Durga Puja with utmost grandeur. Secondly is with their closer ties with the East India Company and later the British Raj in terms of trade and commerce. At least the house of Shobhabazar Rajbari was responsible as the first zamindari house to have a direct connection with an imperial power like the East India Company. Though the East India Company was not interested in taking the political power of Bengal, rather they were more desperate to protect their commercial interests from the Nawab it was only later they realised that they had assumed as the rulers of Bengal in the wake of political vacuum that was created soon after overthrowing the Bengal Nawabi at Plassey in 1757. As Gallagher and Robinson of the Old Cambridge School argues, the British came to acquire the empire through an “absent mind” though they initially came to trade in South Asia (Gallagher and Robinson 1953, pp. 1-15; Porter 2004).⁹ Nevertheless, we see how Durga Puja evolves into a melting pot that stands at the intersection of culture, (political) experience, and economy (Sala 2016).

Figure 23. The Durga idol of Haldar Dutta’s House. Here the goddesses are wearing saris made of golden threads apart from the jewellery they are wearing.

Figure 24. The Durga idol at Gokulchandra Dutta's House, the puja which was started by Shibkrishna Daw.

Figure 25. Left – a lithograph print of English King George V and Queen Mary at the residence of Shibkrishna Daw. This showed their closer affiliations with the English monarchs. It was under their reign when the capital of British India was transferred from Calcutta to Delhi in 1911 at the Third Delhi Durbar. Right – Abhaycharan Mitra's house at Kumartuli.

Figure 26. Foyer inside Shibkrishna Daw's residence. The hanging swords and guns are testimonies to the gunpowder trade they were engaged in. An article from the Anandabazaar Patrika newspaper on 17 March 2017 tells this history.

Figure 27. The entrance and the zamindari house of Shib Krishna Daw.

Speaking of Shibkrishna Daw House (see figure 27), family history state that initially their surname used to be ‘Dutta’ as their founder was Gokulchandra Dutta. He earned immense wealth from his gunpowder trade with the English East India Company. But later when Lord Dalhousie’s infamous Doctrine of Lapse came into effect prior to the 1857 Revolt, Gokulchandra feared that he would lose all his property to the Company as he had no son. Then he adopted his nephew, i.e. his brother Haldar Dutta’s son to save his hard-earned fortune. This nephew was Shibkrishna Daw. Shibkrishna Daw, a rich man himself, having major investments in the railways and in iron, was noted for collecting subscriptions from the rich and famous of the city in order to hold the festivities. He called the collectors of puja subscriptions as fearsome as the government revenue collectors for the Permanent Settlement of Cornwallis that had ruined so many zamindari estates of the times. The 19th Century author Kaliprasanna Singha’s celebrated work *Hutom Pencharnaksha* records the Barowari Puja of Colonial Calcutta and mentions Shibkrishna Daw as the one who started the first Barowari Puja in Calcutta (Nag 1991). Even today, the adjacent houses of Gokulchandra (see figure 24) and Haldar Duttas (see figure 23) still celebrate their own Durga Pujas. Here the images are fully adorned in exquisite gold jewellery designed by the Bengali goldsmiths of those times. That is why urban myths say that Durga first enters this house to get decked in gold jewellery. Since the members of this house are the followers of Visnu, the face of Devi is made on the day of Janmashtami, the day when the birth of Krsna is celebrated.

Khelat Ghose’s Residence – Devi under a Greco-Roman Façade

Calcutta’s opulence of bonedi pujas was coterminous with the building of grand palace-like zamindari mansions which were tangible testimonies of the wealth and power of the zamindars. Among them is Pathuriaghata Rajbari, whose Greco-Roman façade supported by gigantic Indo-Corinthian pillars captures anyone’s attention who walks down the Pathuriaghata Street (see figure 28). It was built by Ramlochan Ghose who worked under the second Governor-General of Bengal, Warren Hastings. This house was constructed and puja was started by his grandson Khelat Chandra Ghose. Khelat Ghose entrusted the famous Martin and Burn Company to construct this impressive mansion. This Martin and Burn Company which was a partnership firm of Sir Rajendranath Mukherjee and Sir Thomas Acquin Martin is known for their iconic landmarks as colonial ensembles in Calcutta like the Metropolitan Building and Grand Hotel Arcade in Esplanade, Victoria Memorial in Queen’s Way, Eden Gardens, Bengal Assembly House, St. Xaviers College in Park Street, to name a few. The thakurdalaan of this mansion is the largest and most impressive of all houses in Calcutta (see figure 29). Like other European-style zamindari houses of Calcutta, this one is not an exception.

Figure 28. The gigantic Greco-Roman façade of Khelat Ghose’s Residence at Pathuriaghata. Popularly known as Pathuriaghata Rajbari.

Figure 29. Left – Durga idol of Khelat Ghose’s House. Right – The impressive thakurdalaan at Khelat Ghose’s House which was built by Martin and Burn Company.

Western (Colonial) Modernity in Durga Puja in the Age of Imperialism

Figure 30. The Durga image of Ekdalia Evergreen Club in Gariahat in South Calcutta. Note the muscular torso of Mahishasura which was a product of the influence of Western Realism Art on indigenous Indian sculptures. Like Gopeshwar Pal, even Ramesh Pal was also known for creating magnificent dynamic posture of Durga. Initially the idol of this pandal was made by Ramesh Pal until he passed away. Ever since then it is now made by his son, the Padma Bhibushan awardee Sanatan Rudra Pal.

With the foundation of British imperialism in Bengal, European thought, styles and culture eventually made its way to Calcutta. This gave rise to ‘babu culture’ - whose half-backed Anglicization and Sankritisation had earned them the title of ejuraj or educated raja and sometimes called Phool Babu as

according to Alope Krishna Deb.¹⁰ In the wake of Zamindari System, babu culture was a product fusion of Western modernity, Mughal and Nawabi courtly cultures and indigenous revivalism inculcating aspects of socio-moral and political changes. Such a phenomenon was inevitable as Dasgupta (2007, pp. 2 – 5) shows the creation of a Cross-Cultural Mentality among the Bengali bourgeois psychology when they were exposed to western ideals of rationalism, science and political ideologies with their former knowledge of Indian past, culture and philosophy. He terms this phenomenon as Universalism.¹¹ Bonedi Durga Puja also underwent changes as their patrons – the babus were exposed to Western influence. For example, staging plays and performances during Durga Puja at the Baganbaari (garden house) of Shobhabazar Rajbari became a common thing during the festivities. Elite Bengalis were more welcoming towards these proscenium plays, most notably to foster Babu-British alliance.¹² In fact, many zamindari houses still practice the tradition of giving a gun salute by shooting a blank fire in the open sky during Sandhi Puja rituals and on Dashami. European art styles in respect to its anatomy also made its influence on the image of the deity. The introduction of English lions in contrast to the horse-faced Vaisnavite horses has already been mentioned before. The gradual influence of Western Realism featuring the image of Mahishasura having a more muscular body resembling Greco-Roman notions of masculinity was a testimony to this fact (see figure 30). This was because colonial rule had imposed radically new models of ‘art’ and ‘artist’ on indigenous society. As Tapati Guha-Thakurta (2015) argues with the coming of new schools of art, Kumartuli clay modellers were being segregated into two diverging halves – one who absorbed the Western academic norms, being regarded as the Western-style ‘artists’ while the other sufficing the demands of the indigenous market, considered as native ‘artisans’. These native artists later advocated Oriental Art with the growing popularity of Orientalist Scholarship as they found the richness in Indian art styles which the colonial state had marginalised for a long time.¹³ For example the legendary artist Gopeshwar Pal (see figure 32) was invited to the British Empire Exhibition at Wembley Park in London in 1924 (see figure 31), where he was highly appraised for his ingenuity in replicating portraits in their exactitude (De 2021, p. 97).

Figure 31. A poster of the British Empire Exhibition of 1924. (Source: Wikipedia)

Figure 32. Gopeshwar Pal in front of his sculpted Durga idol. (Source: The Telegraph Online, <https://www.telegraphindia.com/my-kolkata/durga-puja-special/breaking-the-ekchala-how-myth-became-history/cid/2054575>)

Figure 33. Mahisasuramardini, hand-tinted woodcut print on paper. (Source: DAG Museums)

As Aparajita De (1997) shows, colonial hegemony consciously demarcated a separating line between the ‘bazaar art’ of 19th century available as popular prints in woodcuts (for example see figure 33), lithographs, indigenous clay modelling and stone carving on the one hand, and ‘high art’ of Western Academic realism on the other that resulted in the emergence of artists like Jadunath Pal and Gopeshwar Pal who were being aura-filled with a sense of superiority among their very own associates. Such sieving process of the colonial state created the babus and new artists of Kumartuli that also affected

the image of Durga and Durga Puja rituals in Calcutta and Bengal by extension. Durga's image was also appropriated as Bharat Mata and by extension a saviour of the nation in Nationalist Scholarship. Subsequently, new barowari pujas came up where people fostered and articulated ideas of nationalism and anti-colonialism. Examples are Simla Byam Samiti in Vivekananda Road (see figure 34 right), Baghbazar Sarbojanin in Baghbazar (see figure 34 left), Kumartuli Park Sarbojanin in Kumartuli – all in North Calcutta and Sanatan Dharmotsahini Sabha at Bhawanipur in South Calcutta. In the changing political situations, it is in these barowari pujas where individual artistic expressions gave new identity and shape to the image of Durga. Her dynamic and ferocious warrior like form as described in the Puranas and Śāstric texts (for example see figures 30 and 32), got vividly expressed in the image with the asura now being metaphorically depicted as some political figures starting with the colonial state itself. As a result, Kumartuli gave birth to 'Aarter Thakur'.¹⁴ For instance, Gopeshwar Pal went on to impose Adolf Hitler's portrait as the Asura justifies the fact more pertinently. That asura being imagined as the fascist ruler, Hitler, reflected the artist's conceptual ingenuity that was quite intriguing in Kumartuli clay modelling history (De 2021, p. 99). With the rise of Aarter Thakur from the 20th Century onwards, Durga Puja met Artistic Realism with Political Realism. The most recent example is in 2025 Durga Puja Festivities when the Samaj Sebi Sangha in South Calcutta depicted the English Crown at the feet of Durga as a metaphorical representation of colonial rule as demonic or asuric in nature (see figure 35). How Durga's image was appropriated as by different sabhas and samitis in rituals and discourse is a matter of different discussion.¹⁵

Figure 34. Left – Baghbazar Sarbojanin; Right – Simla Byam Samiti. (Photos clicked by author in 2024)

Conclusion

Festivals, cultures and traditions always serve as live historical texts when interpreted offers fascinating aspects on historical and cultural studies. In this context, the Durga Pujas of Calcutta's zamindari households emerges as a living historical text that shows the dynamic interplay between religion, politics, and culture in colonial Calcutta and Bengal. The bonedi pujas of families such as the Sabarna

Raychaudhuri, the Debs of Shobhabazar, the Daws of Jorasanko, and the Ghose family of Pathuriaghata became arenas where the sacred intertwined with spectacle, serving simultaneously as instruments of social legitimation and cultural negotiation. Eventually, it can be seen how Calcutta's urban landscape got shaped by events and traditions that centered around the Durga Puja festivities. Bonedi pujas became the historical sites of alliance, contestation and projection of power. This was expressed with Durga Puja whose lens offered such a direct projection of power through the ferocious Hindu warrior deity Durga. That power is important to overcome obstacles was synonymous with Durga. With Bengal's religious consciousness directly entrenched in śaktī worship, Durga Puja therefore offered such prospects where the divine met modern contestation of power that ultimately shaped and reshaped Calcutta's urban landscape that even continues even today.

Figure 35. The idol of Samaj Sebi Sangha in 2025. Mahishasura is represented as the English crown where colonialism is metaphorically shown as demonic in nature which Devi as the emerging nation-state annihilated marking the nation's independence from colonial rule.

In contemporary times, this historical continuum finds its recognition in UNESCO's inscription of Kolkata's Durga Puja as intangible cultural heritage—affirming its role as a site of creative continuity and urban belonging. Ultimately, the festival stands out as a multilayered cultural archive through which Bengal's historical experiences of power, colonialism, and modernity continue to express themselves in ritual, art, and collective memory.

Notes

1. UNESCO. "Durga Puja Inscribed on the UNESCO Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity." Unesco.org, 2022, www.unesco.org/en/articles/durga-puja-inscribed-unesco-representative-list-intangible-cultural-heritage-humanity.

2. David Kinsley, who made a survey of the goddesses in the Vedic literature, arrives at the following conclusions. First, none of the Vedic goddesses rivals the great male gods in these texts. Even Ups, the most popular goddess, is rather insignificant, and undoubtedly the male deities dominate the Vedic vision of the divine. Second, although there is evidence that some goddesses like Prithivi and Sarasvati survive in the later Hindu tradition, and the idea of Sakti, though not fully developed, is suggested in the various consorts of the male deities, especially in Indrani, many of the Vedic goddesses simply disappear in the later Hindu tradition. Third, many of the most important goddesses of the later tradition, such as Parvati, Durga, Kali and Radha, are not found at all in Vedic literature. None of the Vedic goddesses is clearly associated with battle or blood sacrifice, both of which are important associations in the myths and cults of several later Hindu goddesses. Finally, there is no single great goddess in the Vedic literature, neither is there any evidence that the authors of the Vedic texts supposed that all the individual goddesses are manifestations of one great goddess. Kinsley thus argues that the great goddess, her various manifestations, and the elaborate mythological ritual structures around them, are late phenomena, the product of a carefully articulated theology that owes very little to the Vedic goddesses. See Kunal Chakrabarti work on Religious Processes (2001, p. 166).

3. Apart from these Halihsahar was a holy place linked to Kalighat through a mud road either running through Chitpur or adjacent to it.

4. Basanta Ray was murdered at the Raydighi pond in Sarshuna in Behala. After this event, Lakhikanta severed all ties with Pratapaditya and came to Kalighat and later forged relations with Aurangzeb who sent his subedar Mansingh to defeat Pratapditya.

5. Shishupati Gangopdhyay was the 11th generation of the family that time.

6. It was one of the three villages that constituted the city of Calcutta along with Sutanuti and Kalikata.

7. Shobhabazar gets its name from Shobharam Basak from whom Nabakrishna purchases the plot of land (13 bighas, 6 katas and 5 chataks) to build his grand mansion. In this palatial house were nachghar (where baijis or courtesans from Lucknow and Benaras used to perform), nahabatkhana, library and a meeting room. He built dewankhanas on Mughal styled Diwani-i-am (General Audience Hall) and Diwani-i-khas (Private Audience Hall) inviting workers from Delhi. Wood workers were brought from Jaipur in Rajasthan. Mural artists were brought from Gaur (Malda) in West Bengal. For a detailed discussion on Nabakrishna Deb's ancestral history and rituals conducted during Durga Puja, see Shubhodip Ray Chaudhuri (2022, pp. 22 – 35).

8. It was the period when traditional institutions of the colonised state were modernised through colonial enlightenment on the grounds of western modernity as colonial modernity. It is through this colonial modernity that the inner domain would become modern borrowing western elements also ensuring the essential marks of native cultural identity are retained. It is through the distinctiveness of preserving one's spiritual culture that the inner domain will claim ascendancy over the outer domain or the colonial state.

9. Both Gallagher and Robinson assert that expansion of the British Empire came through as an "absent mind." The nineteenth century was divided into imperialism and anti-imperialism. These authors show that there was a paradox regarding the expansion of Britain's imperial rule. This contradiction arises even if we confine our attention to the formal empire, as the orthodox viewpoint would force us to do. But if we look beyond into the regions of informal empire, then the difficulties become overwhelming. Since imperialism is the highest stage of capitalism, Britain's expansion in these informal areas were mostly economic and commercial in nature. So whenever there is an economic or commercial weakness, power was imperialistically used to adjust the conditions.

10. Raja Alope Krishna Deb born in 1937 at 36, Nabakrishna Street, Kolkata, he is a retired clerk and seventh in descent from Raja Naba Krishna Deb Bahadur of Shobhabazar Rajbari.
11. Subrata Dasgupta shows these were the hallmarks of the Bengal Renaissance.
12. Baganbaris were spaces to boast elite Bengali wealth to the British. The first initiative to start a baganbari theatre was done by Babu Nabin Chandra Basu organised various spaces in his mansion or rajbari at Shyambazar where a play was staged. He called it Shyambazar Theatre. It is said that Basu spent a handsome amount of Rs.200000/- to stage a play of the 18th Century poem Bidya-Sundar by Bharat Chandra. This trend was taken up by many other rich babus at their mansions like Pyarimohan Bose's Jorasanko Theatre, Metropolitan Theatre at Ramgopal Mallick's palace at Chitpur, Belgachhia Theatre of the Rajas of Paikpara, Shobhabazar Private Theatrical Society by Radhakanta Deb and so on (Chatterjee 2007, pp. 43 – 48).
13. In Kumartuli, this manifested in Netai Chandra Pal modelling the huge figure of Durga with heavy borrowings from Indian classical sculpture that came to be known as Oriental Arter Thakur.
14. Arter Thakur, this particular term got its hold in the domain of Kumartuli during the early decades of 20th century. According to Aparajita De, this particularly suggests that the emphasis on the term 'Arter Thakur' was in itself a variant of the traditional Durga idol and emphasizes on the 'modernity' of the idol, that derived from the specific Western academism taught in the Art school.
15. For detailed discussion see Aparajita De (2021, pp. 100 – 107). Also see Sugata Bose (2017) in his *The Nation as Mother and other visions of Nationhood*, where he argues how the image of nation as Mother was envisioned by Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay in his song *Bande Mataram*, creating controversies over the image of goddess Durga envisioned in the final verse.

Works Cited

- Asokan Inscriptions. Edited by R.G. Basak, Kolkata, Progressive, 1959.
- Bhattacharya, Tithi. "Tracking the Goddess: Religion, Community, and Identity in the Durga Puja Ceremonies of Nineteenth-Century Calcutta." *The Journal of Asian Studies*, vol. 66, no. 4, 2007, pp. 919–962.
- Bhaumik, Sudarshana. "Cosmopolitanism and the Goddess Tradition in Bengal: Situating Mukundaram's Candimangalkavya in the Context of 19th Century Bengal." *Journal of Academic Perspectives*, vol. 1, 2019, pp. 1–26.
- Bose, Sugata. *The Nation as Mother and Other Visions of Nationhood*. New Delhi, Penguin Random House, 2017.
- Chakrabarti, Kunal. *Religious Process: The Purāṇas and the Making of a Regional Tradition*. New Delhi, Oxford University Press, 2001.
- Chakraborty, Soumen. *Sotabdi Prachin: Bonedi Barir Pujor Itihash*. Kolkata, Bhromonpipashu Prokashoni, 2022.
- Chatterjee, Partha. *The Nation and Its Fragments: Colonial and Postcolonial Histories*. Princeton, Princeton University Press, 1993.
- Chatterjee, Sudipto. *The Colonial Staged: Theatre in Colonial Calcutta*. Calcutta; New York, Seagull Books, 2007.
- Chaudhuri, Keshab. *Calcutta: Story of Its Government*. Calcutta, Orient Longman, 1973.

- Chaudhuri, Shubhodip Ray. *Bonedi Kolkatar Durgostab*. Kolikhata Prokashoni, 2022.
- Cudny, Waldemar. "The Phenomenon of Festivals: Their Origins, Evolution, and Classifications." *Anthropos*, vol. 109, no. 2, 2014, pp. 640–656.
- Dasgupta, Subrata. *The Bengal Renaissance: Identity and Creativity from Rammohun Roy to Rabindranath Tagore*. Delhi, Permanent Black, 2007.
- De, Aparajita. "From Religious Festival to Cultural Carnival: Durga Puja and City Branding of Kolkata, India." *Place Event Marketing in the Asia Pacific Region: Branding and Promotion in Cities*, edited by Waldemar Cudny, New York, Routledge, 2021, pp. 107–124.
- Deb, Mrinmoyee. "Manifestation of Icon in the Idol of Goddess Durga in Bengal during the Pre-Independent and Post-Independent Period." *The Making of the Goddess Durga in Bengal: Art, Heritage and the Public*, edited by Samir Kumar Das and Bishnupriya Basak, Singapore, Springer, 2021, pp. 85–112.
- Dutta, Abhijit. *Mother Durga, an Icon of Community and Culture*. Michigan, University of Michigan, 2003.
- Gallagher, John , and Ronald Robinson. "The Imperialism of Free Trade." *Economic History Review*, vol. 6, no. 1, 1953, pp. 1–15.
- Gibson, C., and A. Stewart. *Reinventing Rural Places: The Extent and Impact of Festivals in Rural and Regional Australia*. Wollongong, Australia, University of Wollongong, 2009.
- Marshall, P.J. *Bengal: The British Bridgehead, Eastern India 1740–1828*. *New Cambridge History of India* ed., vol. 2, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1987.
- Mitra, Anjan, and Madhumita Roy. "City, Culture and Public Event - a Temporal Construct." *International Journal of Engineering Research and Development*, vol. 17, no. 2, 2021, pp. 19–29.
- Nair, Thankappan. *Calcutta in the 17th Century*. Calcutta, Firma KLM Private Limited, 1986.
- Porter, Bernard. *The Absent-Minded Imperialists: Empire, Society and Culture in Britain*. New York, Oxford University Press, 2004.
- Sarkar, Bihani. *Heroic Shāktism: The Cult of Durgā in Ancient Indian Kingship*. Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2017.
- Satik Hutom Penchar Naksha. Edited by Arun Nag, Calcutta, Subarnarekha, 1991.
- Sen, Ranjit. *Birth of a Colonial City: Calcutta*. London and New York, Routledge, 2019.
- Sudeshna Banerjee. *Durga Puja : Yesterday, Today and Tomorrow*. New Delhi, Rupa And Co, 2004.
- Taittiriya Āraṇyaka. Poona, Ānandaśrama Sanskrit Series, 1926.
- The Markandeya Puranam*. Translated by F. Eden Pargiter, edited by Joshi K.L. Shastri, Delhi, Parimal Publications, 2004.
- UNESCO. "Durga Puja Inscribed on the UNESCO Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity." *Unesco.org*, 2022, www.unesco.org/en/articles/durga-puja-inscribed-unesco-representative-list-intangible-cultural-heritage-humanity.
- W. Newman & Co. *Handbook to Calcutta*. Calcutta, 1875.
- Yokochi, Yuko. *The Rise of the Warrior-Goddess in Ancient India: A Study of the Myth of Kauśikī-Vindhyavāsīnī in the Skanda-Purāṇa*. 2004.